

THE COLOR OF STILLNESS

| WAYAN KARJA

August 2025

Gallery DIE ERSTE ETAGE

Wilhelmsburg, Rubbertstraße 25, 21109

Hamburg

Aromas from the past still linger in me. The smells of paint, oil, acrylic, fixative, charcoals, and pastels—an artist's studio, a haven of creation—come back in waves of sentimentality. The hustle and bustle, the uncertainty that rewards certainty, the beauty within the chaos unveiling a new life through a painting.

My grandfather was a farmer who painted after the tourist boom in the '70s. My father became interested in painting as a young boy and eventually became an artist and educator. I soon became familiar with this environment and from a tender age, not long after I was able to chase dragonflies through the paddy fields, my father's canvas, paper, and colors became mine too. My younger brother, one year apart, was no different. He tagged along and would paint with me until we forgot to eat!

My father was generous with us. He even dedicated a wall for all our creations. He would consider our paintings very serious as if grading his students at the university. After tilting his head to the right—then to the left, after a long momentary pause, arms crossed firmly to the chest or on his hips, Bapak, as we called him, would supply feedback, "You are well with colors and your brother has better control over form". He always gave more than a nod. It made us think we were just one step away from creating a masterpiece, from being a Da Vinci. Hence we kept on going.

At home, life was never dull. While waiting for a painting to dry, we would play in the rice fields or dive deep into otherworldly dimensions through heavy (literally) art books that were always pleasant to look at—and sniff at.

This environment shaped me into who I am today: I make art, write about art, curate shows, research art archives, etc. I dive deep into this art world because, as clichè as it may sound, this is the only world that has become home to me.

I acknowledge that these privileges are here because of sacrifices—to our elders, past and present, to the generosity of my *Bapak*, Wayan Karja, and my *Emek*, Madé Sistiani.

Summer 2023. I found myself in one of the most beautiful places I've ever been to. A lovely small house, with a modern interior, a patio, a green well-tended lawn, and the most spectacular view of the river. Boats and soaring birds were everywhere. The sky was often blue, the sunset red-orangeish, and the night as calm as it may be. After a few weeks, I felt that I had become part of this environment.

I collected leaves, flowers, stalks, and anything I could find. Once in a while, when there was time to go to the city center, I would visit Modulor. The stark contrast between heavily industrialized art materials and something simply found in my walk fascinates me. I soon created collages inspired by this duality. I was also fascinated by the death of trees in the forests and how they stayed there to become a kind of fleeting monument.

One time we had a discussion at the NoGallery, the conversation was on women artists in Bali and Eurocentric predominant views underlying Balinese Art Histories. During this event, just like many other events I had the chance to attend during my residency in Schwanenwerder, I met people from all walks of life, each contributing to my experience in Berlin.

Now, almost two years have passed since the residency. Life goes on but the experience lingers.

Ni Putu Sridiniari

The Color of Stillness

In my work, I follow the path of cosmic color, the sacred tones that shape the universe in Balinese belief. Each color has its meaning: white, red, black, yellow, and the center as a blend of all. These colors hold energy and connect us to nature and the divine.

In Balinese art, color is more than beauty it is prayer, spirit, and balance. My painting becomes a mandala, a space where all directions meet in harmony. Through this, I aim to convey the profound rhythm of life and our place within the cosmos.

The Color of Shiva, 2010

Acrylic on Canvas

150 x 290 cm

Underwater, 2021
Acrylic on Canvas
150 x 100 cm

Starry Night, 2018

Acrylic on Canvas

200 x 180 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2012

Acrylic on Canvas

120 x 150 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2014

Acrylic on Canvas

120 x 150 cm

Cosmic Dark Blue, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

210 x 150 cm

The Beginning, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
120 x 120 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
117 x 117 cm

Wilderness, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
80 x 120 cm

Yellow Field, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

80 x 120 cm

Cosmic Yellow, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

90 x 120 cm

Blossom, 2022

Acrylic on Canvas

110 x 140 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

80 x 110 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

80 x 120 cm

Metamorphosis, 2023

Acrylic on Canvas
200 x 100 cm

Explosion, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
150 x 120 cm

The Color of Stillness, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
80 x 120 cm

Flower Field, 2025

Acrylic on Canvas

142 x 85 cm

Gaia Vortex, 2024
Acrylic on Canvas
200 x 160 cm

Pangider Bhuwana Color, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
200 x 200 cm

Cosmic Energy, 2016

Acrylic on Canvas

200 x 200 cm (2 panel)

@ 200 x 100

Wilderness, 2024
Acrylic on Canvas
200 x 100 cm

Cosmic Turquoise Blue, 2025

Acrylic on canvas

200 x 300 cm (3 panel)

@ 200 x 100

Deep Blue, 2025
Acrylic on Canvas
120 x 75 cm

Ceteredness, 2020
Acrylic on Canvas
60 x 80 cm

Energy Line, 2025
Pen, watercolor on paper
52 x 42 cm

EDUCATION

- 2016- 2020 Doctorate Program of Religion and Culture, Hindu University of Indonesia, Denpasar, Bali
- 2008 – 2010 Expressive Arts, European Graduate School, Switzerland, Europe.
- 1997 – 1999 Master of Fine Arts, Painting and Printmaking, University of South Florida, USA.
- 1985 – 1990 Painting, Udayana University, Denpasar, Bali.
- 1981 – 1985 Painting High School of Fine Arts, Denpasar, Bali
- 1978 – 1981 Junior High School (SMPN 1 Ubud) extracurricular painting; study painting from Ketut Sujana, Penestanan.
- 1972 – 1977 Elementary School (SD 1 Sayan); painting young artist style of Penestanan from Ketut Santra (father).

SOLO EXHIBITIONS

- 2025 Art Exhibition, The Color of Stillness, NoGallery, Berlin, Germany.
Art exhibition, The Color of Stillness, Franziska und Tim Cordts Stiftung, Hamburg, Germany.
Art Exhibition, Beyond the Unknown, Live Space, Jakarta Post.
- 2022 Art Exhibition “Dark to Light”, A Retrospective 1982-2022. Karja Art Space, Ubud, Bali.
- 2018 Art Exhibition “Cosmic Energy”, CSIS Jakarta.
- 2015 Art Exhibition Wayan Karja, “Recent Paintings: Journey to the Unknown”, CSIS Jakarta.
- 2013 Art Exhibition Ganesha Gallery, Jimbaran, Bali.
- 2008 Art Exhibition “Aesthetic and Sublime,” CSIS Jakarta.
- 2006 Art Exhibition “Silence,” West Australian School of Yoga, Perth, Australia.
Art Exhibition Ganesha Gallery, Four Seasons Resort Bali, Jimbaran, Bali.
- 2005 Art Exhibition “Spiritual colors,” Trotte Museum, Arlesheim, Switzerland.
- 2004 Art Exhibition “Karja,” CSIS, Jakarta.
Art Exhibition Chouinard Gallery, Chicago, USA. Art Exhibition “Blue of Karja,” Gaya Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- 2003 Art Exhibition Chouinard Gallery, Hong Kong.
Art Exhibition “The colors of Life,” West Australian School of Yoga, Perth, Australia.
Art Exhibition “Panca Warna,” Scala, Basel, Switzerland.
- 2002 Art Exhibition “Pangider Bhuwana: The colors of Life,” Stadt museum Crailsheim, Germany.
- 2001 Art Exhibition Chouinard Gallery, Hong Kong.
Art Exhibition Santra Putra Gallery, Penestanan Kaja, Ubud, Bali.

- 2000 Art Exhibition Santra Putra Gallery, Penestanan Kaja, Ubud, Bali.
 Art Exhibition "Emptiness," Gallery Sembilan, Ubud, Bali.
 Art Exhibition "Pengider Bhuwana: The Colors of Life," Kloster Dornach, Switzerland.
- 1999 Art Exhibition Déjà vu Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
 Art Exhibition Teaching Gallery, Tampa, Florida, USA.
 Art Exhibition Christopher C. Brodigan Gallery, Groton School, Massachusetts, USA.
 Art Exhibition Syzygy Gallery, Fort Myers, Florida, USA.
- 1998 Art Exhibition "Past and Present," Centre Gallery, Tampa, Florida, USA.
 Art Exhibition Syzygy Gallery, Fort Myers, Florida, USA.
- 1996 Art Exhibition Knoll Gallery, Basel, Switzerland.
- 1992 Art Exhibition The Gallery Tjampuhan, Ubud Bali.

SELECTED GROUP EXHIBITION

2024

- Art Exhibition at Non Frasa Gallery, Ubud, Bali
- Art Exhibition at Shanghai Art Museum, China.
- Visual Art Exhibition, 'Rupa Harmoni Berdikari Negeri,' PTSI, Gedung D Depdikbudristek, Jakarta.
- Art Exhibition, 'Surya Segara Rupa' Santrian Gallery, Sanur, Bali.
- Art Exhibition, Polandia, Europe.

2023

- Art Exhibition Bali Dwipatara Adirupa: Contemplation, Nata Citta Art Space, ISI Bali.
- Art Exhibition Art Moment, Gaia: Mother Nature, Inter-Continental, Hotels & Resorts, Jimbaran, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Bali Mega Rupa: Ocean, ARMA Museum, Ubud, Bali.

2022

- Art Exhibition Bali Megarupa. Cosmic Energy, Museum Neka, Ubud, Bali
- Art Exhibition Bali Padma Bhuwana, Bali-Bhuwana Rupa The International Art
- Art Exhibition dengan judul Dharma-Tirta-Prana "Kehidupan Tanpa Henti."
- Art Exhibition Awakening, Art Exhibition Teh Villa Gallery, Surabaya.
- Exhibition Art Jakarta, Jakarta Convention Center, Jakarta.
- Art Exhibition Bali Dwipantara Adirupa, Virtual Exhibition. ISI Denpasar
- Art Exhibition Konvergensi: Pasca Tradisionalisme. Galeri Katamsi ISI Yogyakarta.

- Art Exhibition Bali Padma Bhuwana Argha-Tirtha-Sidhi.
- Art Exhibition Waskita II, Teh Villa Gallery, Surabaya.
- Art Exhibition Bali Padma Bhuwana Argha-Tirtha-Sidhi. Nata Citta Art Space, ISI Bali.
- Art Exhibition Bali-Bhuwana Rupa The International Art Exhibition:Dharma-Tirta-Prana Peserta. Nata Citta Art Space, ISI Bali.

2021

- Art Exhibition Bali Megarupa III, ARMA Museum, Ubud.
- Art Exhibition Bali Sangga Dwipantara

2020

- Art Exhibition "Forgotten." Sin Sin Gallery, Hong Kong.

2019

- Art Exhibition Panca Maha Bhuta, Museum ARMA, Ubud. Bali.
- Art Exhibition "Balinese Masters: Aesthetic DNA Trajectories of Balinese Visual Arts," ABBC Nusa Dua Bali.

2018

- Art Exhibition: Drawing, Exhibition in Japan.

2017

- Art Exhibition Pesta Kesenian Bali, Art Center Denpasar, Bali.
- "Change" Museum Puri Lukisan Ubud. Bali.

2016

- Art Exhibition "The Poem of Colors," Group Seni Murni ISI Denpasar, Neka
- Art Museum, Ubud Bali.
- Art Exhibition Group Seni Murni ISI Denpasar, Monkey Forest Gallery, Ubud, Bali.

2015

- Art Exhibition The Journey of the Indonesian Abstract Art, "Soulscape In Progress #3" Bentara Budaya Bali

2014

- Art Exhibition "Etnicpower," Art Center Denpasar Bali.

Art Exhibition Wayan Karja (Bali) and Della Burford (Canada), Santra Putra Gallery, Ubud, Bali

2013

- Art Exhibition University of Western Australia, Perth.
- Art Exhibition Puri Menggah Gallery, Gianyar Bali.

2009

- Art Exhibition Pecs Galeria, Pecs City, Hungary, Europe.
- Art Exhibition “Two Artists“ Paia Contemporary Gallery, Maui, Hawaii, USA.

2008

- Art Exhibition Neka Art Museum, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Three Artists, “Paia Contemporary Gallery, Maui, Hawaii, USA.

2007

- Art Exhibition Taman Budaya Mataram, Lombok.
- Art Exhibition The National Gallery, Jakarta.

2006

- Art Exhibition “Niskala: The Indonesian Abstract Painters,” Sika Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Neka Art Museum, Ubud, Bali.

2005

- Art Exhibition “Seni Lukis Gianyar,” Gallery YDBA, Jakarta.
- Art Exhibition “Our Spirit, Our Mother, Our Country,” Laurence Wilson Gallery, University of Western Australia, Perth, Australia.
- Art Exhibition “The 10th Anniversary of Museum Rudana,” Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Art for Compassion,” Grand Hyatt Hotel, Jakarta.

2004

- Art Exhibition ISI Denpasar, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Gaya Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Jejak Tradisi dalam Ekspresi Modern II,” Museum H. Widayat, Magelang.
- Art Exhibition “Jejak Tradisi dalam Ekspresi Modern III,” Puri Art Gallery, Malang.

2003

- Art Exhibition “Bali-Basel,” Sika Gallery, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Indonesian Art Festival (FKI) III,” Surabaya.
- Art Exhibition “Jejak Tradisi dalam Ekspresi Modern I,” Gedung Socityet, Yogyakarta.
- Art Exhibition “Swiss Cow in Bali,” GWK, Jimbaran, Bali.

2002

- Art Exhibition Gaya Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Dua Hati 2 – Evening of the Double Heart,” poetry and art collaboration: Elizabeth and Wayan Karja, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Rudana Museum, Ubud, Bali.

2001

- Art Exhibition “Dua Hati 1– Evening of the Double Heart,” poetry and art collaboration: Elizabeth and Wayan Karja, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “SHUL: International Art Collaboration,” Sika Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Rotary Art Exhibition,” Maya Gallery, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Rotary Art Exhibition,” Rudana Museum, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Gaya Gallery, Ubud, Bali.

2000

- Art Exhibition “Festival Nusa Dua,” Bali.
- Art Exhibition arranged by Rudana Museum in Italy.

1999

- Art Exhibition “Bali Welcomes the Third Millennium,” Rudana Museum, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Gallery STSI, Denpasar, Bali.

1998

- Art Exhibition “Great Mother and the New Father,” Maine, USA.
- Art Exhibition, Art and Java Gallery, Tampa, Florida, USA.

1997

- Art Exhibition “Bali Art Selection,” STSI Denpasar, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “Indonesian – Japan,” Tokyo, Japan.
- Art Exhibition The permanent collection at Lata Mahosadi Museum, STSI Denpasar, Bali.
- Art Exhibition “MFA Exhibition,” Centre Gallery, Tampa, Florida, USA.
- Art Exhibition “MFA Exhibition,” Mahaffey Theatre, Saint Petersburg, Florida, USA.

1996

- Art Exhibition Neka Art Museum, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Rudana Museum, Ubud, Bali.

1995

- Art Exhibition Tata Ubud, Cahaya Dewata, Ubud, Bali.
- Art Exhibition Training Expo '95, Jakarta.
- Art Exhibition Neka Art Museum, Ubud, Bali.

1993

- Art Exhibition Festival of Contemporary Art, STSI, Denpasar, Bali; collage contemporary.

1991

- Art Exhibition “Keluarga Bayangkara,” Neka Museum, Ubud, Bali.

1990

- Art Exhibition “Sanggar Seni Rupa,” Bali Museum, Denpasar, Bali.

1989

- Art Exhibition with Program Study of Fine Art and Design Faculty, Udayana University, at Bali Museum, Denpasar Bali.

1988

- Art Exhibition “Penestanan Group,” Puri Lukisan Museum, Ubud, Bali.

1987

- Art Exhibition at Museum Bali, Denpasar, Bali: impressionist style of painting.
- Art Exhibition “Triennale I Indonesian Paintings,” Art Centre, Denpasar, Bali.

1986

- Art Exhibition Club Med, Nusa Dua, Bali: Impressionist painting result of 1st-year study at Udayana University.
- Art Exhibition Museum Puri Lukisan, Ubud, Bali: Impressionist painting result of 1st year of study at Udayana University.

1984

- Art Exhibition Nusa Dua Beach Hotel, Bali: flora and fauna and the academic influence of landscape as background.

1983

- Art Exhibition Nusa Dua Beach Hotel, Bali: Flora and Fauna in Ubud style of painting.

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

2016-2022	Head of the Village (Adat) the village of Penestanan Kaja, Ubud, Bali.
2015	Steering Committee of the Art Event "Painting 1000 Meters," Gianyar, Bali.
2010	Art Competition and Exhibition, Pech Gallery, Hungaria. Europe.
2007	Guest Speaker, The International Symposium on Inter-cultural Understanding and Co-operation, Bangkok, Thailand.
2006	Lecture, University of Sam Ratulangi, Manado, North Sulawesi. Lecture, Muhamadiyah University, Mataram, Lombok.
2005	Speaker at the Symposium Universal Relationships and Responsibilities, University of Western Australia, Perth, Australia.
2004 – 2008	Dean Faculty of Fine Arts and Design, Indonesian Institute of the Arts (ISI), Denpasar, Bali.
2004-2008	Head of the Senator of the Faculty of Fine Arts and Design, ISI Denpasar, Bali.
2004-2008	Member of the Senator at the ISI Denpasar, Bali.
2003 – 2008	Annual Reviewer and Jury for the Fair of National Scientific and Creativity, Directorate General of Higher Education, Department of National Education, Republic of Indonesia.
2002 – 2004	Head of the Fine Arts Dept., Indonesian College of the Arts (STSI), Denpasar, Bali.
2000-2004	Member of Senator of the STSI Denpasar, Bali.

- 2002 Painting Instructor, Sommer Akademie, Akademie Schloss Rotenfels, Gaggenau-Bad Rotenfels, Germany
- 2001 – 2004 Instructor, Fine Arts at IKIP PGRI, Bali.
- 1997 – 1999 Instructor, University of South Florida, Tampa, Florida, USA.
- 1995 Restorer of paintings in a workshop at Agung Rai Museum of Art, Bali; Arranged by the Goethe Institute, Germany with the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia.
- 1993 – Present Faculty member of the Indonesian Institute of the Arts, Denpasar, Bali
- 1990 – 1996 Teacher at the School of Fine Arts (SMSR), Ubud, Bali.
- 1989 with his family Built the Santra Putra: art studio (Karja Art Space), Guest House, and training facilities.
- 1984 The transition of the profession towards the end of study at a fine arts school in Denpasar: making batik employs some teenagers around, continues to study at university, become full-time artist, or become a teacher at the situation father's sick.

GRANTS AND AWARDS:

- 2022 Satya Lancana Karya Satya 20 Tahun, President Republic of Indonesia.
- 2010 Art Commissioned, Macau, MFA Asia Ltd., Hong Kong.
- 2008 Exhibition of Indonesia International Education and Culture 2008, Indonesia Edu culture Center, Malaysia.
Satya Lancana Karya Satya 10 Tahun, President Republic of Indonesia.
- 2006 Directorate General of Higher Education, Indonesia.
Nakasone Yasuhiro Award, Japan.
- 2005 Directorate General of Higher Education, Indonesia.
- 2002 Ministeriums fur Kultur, Jugend, und Sport, Germany.
- 1999 Mugde Fellowship, artist in residence, Groton School, Massachusetts, USA.
- 1998 Diversity Awards, Great Mother and the New Father, Maine, USA.
- 1997 Excellence Faculty Awards, International College of Art, Denpasar, Bali.
Grant for Master of Fine Arts degree, University of South Florida, Florida, USA.
- 1996 Excellence Faculty Awards, International College of Art, Denpasar, Bali.
- 1991, 1994, 1995, 1996, 1997, 2001, 2005 Bali Art Festival Artist, Bali.

REVIEWS/BOOK:

- Wayan Seriyoga Parta, Made Susanta Dwitanaya, dan Dewa Gede Purwita. 2022. I Wayan Karja: Bernalar Dalam Warna Melukis Dengan Rasa. (book) Yogyakarta: Pustaka Larasan, 2022.
- Dewa Gede Purwita Purwita. Terapi Seni I Wayan Karja. (Artikel Jurnal). SENADA (Seminar Nasional Manajemen, Desain dan Aplikasi Bisnis Teknologi). 2022.
- Jean Couteau, I Wayan Karja, Cosmic Energy. Jakarta, 2018.
- Richard Horstman. Wayan Karja: From a 'young artist' to Balinese Visionary. Life as Art Asia, November 18, 2016.
- Liza Yosephine, "I Wayan Karja draws inspiration from the Energy of Colors." The Jakarta Post, Fri, August 3, 2018.
- Richard Horstman, Magazine Ubud Life, June-August, 2015.
- Karya Seni Bali dari Seniman I Wayan Karja, Indopost, Minggu, 8 Maret, 2015.
- Wayan Juniarta, The perseverance of Wayan Karja, The Jakarta Post, 2015.
- Seniman Bali Menerobos Hegemoni Barat, Kompas: Kamis, February 26, 2015.
- Niken Prathivi, I Wayan Karja in Search of Expression, The Jakarta Post, Thursday, February 26, 2015.
- I Wayan Seriyoga Parta, Journey to the Unknown, exhibition catalog, CSIS Jakarta, 2015.
- Ekspresi Nilai Lokal Bali di atas Kanvas, Kompas: Jumat, 6 Maret, 2015.
- Niken Prathivi, I Wayan Karja: Thinking in the Abstract. The Jakarta Post, Monday, 6 March 2015.
- Koes Karnadi: Executive Art Editor, Modern Indonesian Art, 2nd revised edition, Denpasar, Koes Artbooks, 2010
- I Wayan Juniarta, "Turning Point," Weekender magazine, The Jakarta Post, March 2008.
- Koes Kamadi: Executive Art Editor, Modern Indonesian Art, 1st edition, Denpasar, Koes Artbooks, 2006.
- Agus Dermawan T., "Lukisan-Lukisan I Wayan Karja: Spiritualitas Bali dalam Esensi," exhibition catalogue, CSIS, Jakarta, December 2004.
- Jean Couteau, "Wayan Karja's Minimalist Symbolism," The Jakarta Post, November 30, 2004.
- Bali Rebound, "Blue of Karja Represents Contemplative Works, Art & Culture," April 17 - May 01, 2004.
- Fred Camper, "Out of This World," Section One, Chicago Reader, Chicago, March 19, 2004.
- Joseph Foley, "Bridging, Blurring, Unifying: I Wayan Karja," Washington D.C., February 6, 2004.
- Hckl, "I Wayan Karja im Scala: Die Farben des Lebens," Basler Zeitung, Samstag/Sonntag, Switzerland, November 8-9, 2003, Nr.261.

Rita A. Widiadana, "Artist Incorporates Universality in Balinese Roots," The Jakarta Post, January 19, 2003.

Urs Ramseyer, "The Power Beyond the Pictures," Scala, Basel, Switzerland, 2003.

Sacksteter, „Ziel ist Harmonie: Balinesischer Künstler befasst sich mit Farbe,“ Kultur, (Crailsheim Germany), July 27, 2002.

Ketut Sutika, „Wayan Karja Gelar Pameran Di Jerman,“ Antara, June 8, 2002.

Mernet Larsen, "Wayan Karja," catalogue, Tampa, Florida, 2002.

Jean Couteau, "Shul: Int'l Experiment in Installation and Performance Art," The Jakarta Post, May 10, 2001.

Daniel Boillat, „Ausstellung ‚Pengider Bhuana‘ von I Wayan Karja,“ Kloster Dornach, Switzerland, September 5, 2000.

Doplang, "I Wayan Karja Pengider Bhuwana: The Color of Life," Bali Travel News, April 28 - May 11, 2000.

KMB, "I Wayan Karja Membudayakan Kritik," Bali Post, Jumat Pon, April 7, 2000.

Katherine Collier, "The Mudge Fellow: A Balinese Outlook in a Massachusetts Setting," The Circle Voice ARTS, Massachusetts., April 30, 1999.

Suyadnyana, "Perjalanan Seni Karja Dimulai di Luar Negeri," Bali Post Minggu Keliwon, September 22, 1996.

Urs Ramseyer, "I Wayan Karja Ubud/Bali," Galeri Niklaus Knoll, Switzerland, September 14, 1996.

Wayan Karja ist ein bildender Künstler, der durch seinen unverwechselbaren Einsatz von Farbe die balinesische Tradition mit zeitgenössischer Kunst verbindet. Für Karja ist Farbe mehr als eine ästhetische Wahl; sie ist eine kulturelle und spirituelle Sprache, die grenzenlose Ausdrucksmöglichkeiten eröffnet. Geleitet von der balinesischen Farbphilosophie erforscht seine Praxis einen sensiblen und tiefgründigen, spirituell-kosmologischen Dialog. Das Eintauchen in Farbe wird dabei zu einem Mittel, Bedeutung, Energie und kulturelle Tiefe zu vermitteln. Die Lehre war schon immer ein wesentlicher Bestandteil seines Weges. Durch den fortlaufenden Austausch mit Studierenden und der weiteren Kunstgemeinschaft erneuert und stärkt Karja kontinuierlich seinen kreativen Prozess. Dieser Dialog stellt sicher, dass seine Arbeit lebendig und relevant bleibt, lokal wie global Resonanz findet und die Tradition in einem zeitgenössischen Kontext neu verankert.

I Wayan Karja is a visual artist who bridges Balinese tradition with contemporary art through his distinctive use of color. For Karja, color is more than an aesthetic choice; it is a cultural and spiritual language that opens limitless dimensions of expression. Guided by the Balinese philosophy of color, his practice explores a sensitive and profound spiritual cosmological dialogue, where immersion in color becomes a way to convey meaning, energy, and cultural depth. Teaching has always been an integral part of his journey. Through ongoing dialogue with students and the wider art community, Karja continuously renews and strengthens his creative process. This exchange ensures that his work remains vibrant and relevant, resonating with audiences both locally and globally while affirming tradition in a contemporary context.

*“light gives birth to color,
color awakens feeling,
feeling leads to awareness”*

Franziska & Tim Cordts Stiftung
www.cordts-stiftung.de
Wayan Karja, www.wayankarja.com

